

Project based curriculum: multi-case analysis from Brazilian public universities

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Abstract

Driven by changes in workforce demands and educational policies, Brazilian engineering programs are encouraged to adopt active learning strategies to enhance student engagement and align curricula with contemporary challenges. This study investigates the integration of project-based learning (PBL) in engineering education in Minas Gerais. A document analysis of 219 Pedagogical Project Programs (PPPs) revealed that 40 explicitly incorporated active methodologies. Based on Helle et al.'s (2006) classification, 55% of the projects were implemented as components, 24% as exercises, and 21% adopted a project-oriented curriculum. To explore the characteristics of the latter group, a multi-case study was conducted involving two programs: Mechanical Engineering at IFMG Arcos and Electronic Engineering at UNIFEI Itajubá. Data collection involved a combination of document analysis, semi-structured interviews, and a literature review, followed by content analysis. Results highlight key factors for successful implementation, including institutional support, faculty engagement, curriculum flexibility, and resistance management. IFMG's model is based on Integrative Academic Works spanning all semesters, while UNIFEI's curriculum integrates PBL with competency-based education and progressive student autonomy. Despite contextual differences, both cases highlight the importance of aligning curriculum design with labour market needs, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration, and incorporating authentic engineering challenges. The findings contribute to the discourse on curriculum innovation, offering practical insights for institutions seeking to adopt or refine project-based curricula. This research is part of the Engineering Teaching Observatory Project and was supported by FAPEMIG.

Keywords: Active Learning; Engineering Education; Conference Information; Project Approaches.

1 Introduction

The demands of the modern workforce and the evolving characteristics of current generations have driven higher education institutions to seek innovative approaches for modernising education. This transformation is particularly evident in Brazil, where recent curricular guidelines for engineering programs emphasise competency-based education, active learning, and the integration of digital educational technologies. Among these strategies, Project-Based Learning (PBL) has emerged as a transformative tool for fostering meaningful learning and increasing student engagement. By immersing students in real-world projects, PBL not only bridges the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application but also inspires a new generation of engineers ready to tackle the dynamic challenges of their profession.

Despite its recognised benefits, implementing PBL in engineering education presents significant challenges. When applied beyond individual exercises or isolated components, a comprehensive PBL-oriented approach necessitates fundamental curricular innovation across entire programs. This transformation requires a shift in pedagogical models, faculty development, assessment methods, and institutional support structures. This study examines the adoption of active learning strategies in engineering programs at higher education institutions in Minas Gerais, Brazil.

An analysis of the Pedagogical Project Programs (PPPs) from 219 engineering courses across the state revealed that 40 programs explicitly incorporate active learning methodologies. Based on Helle et al.'s (2006) classification, 55% of these programs integrate projects as components, 24% employ projects as exercises, and 21% embrace projects as the primary orientation for learning. To further explore the implications of PBL-oriented curricula, this study presents a multi-case analysis of two engineering programs that have embraced this model. Through documentary analysis, interviews, and content analysis, the study identifies key factors, including motivators, change agents, institutional contexts, and challenges associated with implementing Problem-Based Learning (PBL).

The study aims to provide valuable insights for other Brazilian engineering programs considering similar curricular innovations by examining these cases. The findings make a significant contribution to the ongoing discourse on curriculum modernisation, engaging institutions in a shared academic conversation and providing practical guidance for those seeking to enhance engineering education through active learning methodologies.

This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides a theoretical discussion on Curriculum Innovation and Project-Based Learning, offering a comprehensive overview of the concepts and their relevance to engineering education; Section 3 outlines the methodological procedures used in the study; Section 4 presents the two PBL-oriented curricula cases from UNIFEI and IFMG Arcos; Section 5 discusses the results of the data analysis; Section 6 offers the conclusions drawn from the study; and finally, Section 7 contains the references that support this research.

2 Engineering in Motion: Curriculum Innovation and Project-Based Learning

Changes in labor market demands and new educational guidelines drive the need to reformulate engineering curricula. In Brazil, the National Curriculum Guidelines (DCNs) encourage innovative approaches, such as competency-based education and active methodologies. To train competent engineers, Powell and Weenk (2003) highlight the importance of integrating technical knowledge and interpersonal skills through learning environments that simulate real-world challenges. Furthermore, Keller-Franco and Masetto (2018) point out that traditional approaches, which focus on disciplinary fragmentation and lecture-based teaching, hinder the connection between theory and practice.

Project-Based Learning (PBL) has been widely advocated as a solution to the challenges of engineering education. Helle et al. (2006) emphasise that methodologies such as PBL foster meaningful learning by placing students in authentic problem-solving situations. Vieira Júnior et al. (2017) reinforce this perspective by demonstrating that students exposed to active methodologies, such as PBL, show higher engagement and better knowledge retention throughout their studies.

Project-based learning can be structured in different ways. Helle et al. (2006) identify three levels of PBL implementation:

- Projects as exercises: specific activities within courses.
- Projects as components: courses or modules structured around projects.
- Projects as orientation: an entire curriculum organised based on projects.

The project-based curriculum model offers several advantages, including the development of student autonomy, promotion of interdisciplinarity, and connection to real-world work problems. Keller-Franco and Masetto (2018) emphasise that these elements are crucial for ensuring that students acquire competencies aligned with contemporary societal needs. The project-based curriculum model is also explored by Powell and

Weenk (2003), who describe the experience of the University of Twente with Project-Led Engineering Education (PLEE). This model emphasises collaborative learning and real-world problem-solving as core strategies for engineering education. Weenk and Blij (2011) reinforce the importance of curricular adaptation to ensure the effectiveness of project-based learning, highlighting the need for institutional support and structural changes.

In the Brazilian context, Keller-Franco and Masetto (2018) analyse the implementation of a project-based curriculum at a higher education institution, highlighting its contribution to a more integrated and contextualised education. Similarly, Vieira Júnior (2018) analyses an engineering course based on projects at the Federal Institute of Minas Gerais (IFMG) - Campus Arcos, emphasising that this model can reduce dropout rates and increase student engagement. Vieira Júnior et al. (2017) illustrate how project-based curricula enhance student engagement and practical knowledge application by integrating theory and hands-on problem-solving across the engineering program.

The implementation of PBL in engineering education presents significant challenges. Powell and Weenk (2003) state that transitioning from a traditional curriculum to a project-based one requires profound structural changes, including the development of new assessment formats, the reformulation of teaching materials, and faculty training. Weenk and Blij (2011) reinforce that successful implementation depends on collaboration among faculty, students, and institutional administrators. Vieira Júnior et al. (2017) also note that adapting PBL in Brazilian institutions presents additional challenges, including teacher training and aligning theory and practice within existing curricula.

Helle et al. (2006) also highlight that adopting PBL must be accompanied by careful planning to prevent projects from becoming isolated activities disconnected from the rest of the curriculum. Vieira Júnior (2018) demonstrates that adapting this model to Brazilian reality necessitates structural changes and the involvement of the entire academic community to overcome resistance.

Therefore, analysing engineering programs that have adopted the PBL-oriented approach allows for an understanding of how different institutions have structured their curricula and what challenges and benefits emerge from this adoption. Comparative studies can reveal best practices and effective strategies to overcome barriers, thereby contributing to the improvement of engineering education and the more efficient implementation of this innovative approach.

3 Materials and Methods

This study follows a descriptive research approach (Gonçalves & Meirelles, 2002), the most suitable method for analysing curriculum innovations such as project-oriented curricula. A qualitative research strategy was employed to gain an in-depth understanding of the history and unique characteristics of each case. According to Gonçalves & Meirelles (2002), this approach efficiently describes social phenomena and behaviours within their contexts.

A multiple case study was conducted to achieve the study's objectives. As Yin (2005) highlights, numerous case studies are valuable for testing theories and clarifying complex situations. The research focused on two engineering programs that implemented project-oriented curricula. The first case examined the Mechanical Engineering Program at the Federal Institute of Minas Gerais (IFMG) – Arcos campus. Integrative Academic Works (IAW) were introduced each semester, characterising the program's project-based orientation. The second case analysed the Electronic Engineering Program at the Federal University of Itajubá (UNIFEI), which progressively adopted a Competence- and Project-Based Curriculum, exposing students to design and project techniques from their studies.

Data collection was conducted through three complementary methods: first, interviews were held with two professors—one from each institution—who played key roles in the curriculum innovation process as members of the management committee responsible for overseeing its implementation; second, document analysis was carried out, focusing on the pedagogical project plans (PPP) of both programs to gain a deeper understanding of their specific features; and third, a bibliographic review was performed, drawing on academic papers and book chapters that had previously discussed both cases, thereby offering valuable insights for their analysis.

A content analysis was conducted, integrating theoretical perspectives with the case descriptions, leading to a comprehensive discussion of the findings.

4 Case Studies

This section presents the two case studies analysed in this paper, outlining their history, key innovation agents, challenges, and program structure. Both cases are described based on interviews, documents, and relevant literature available on the subject.

4.1 Case 1: Integrative Academic Work in Mechanical Engineering - Federal Institute of Minas Gerais (IFMG) - Arcos campus

This first case study is from the Federal Institute of Minas Gerais (IFMG), specifically from the Arcos campus, which features a mechanical engineering program designed through Integrative Academic Works (IAW). The professor who described the case was a prominent leader of this movement. The interviewee stated that his motivation for proposing this curricular innovation stemmed from his educational background and prior involvement in pioneering programs, such as the Energy Engineering course at PUC Minas. Upon analysing this program, the interviewee identified an opportunity to design a curriculum that would align with Brazil's national educational guidelines, which are often overlooked in traditional programs. In 2016, he led the creation of a Mechanical Engineering course structured entirely around project-based learning. The foundation of this curriculum is a mandatory subject known as Integrative Academic Work (IAW), present throughout all ten semesters of the program. In each IAW, students engage in practical projects that synthesise the content from their other courses, promoting hands-on learning from the outset of their academic journey.

Within the scope of IAW, each student project is supervised by a lead professor and supported by instructors from related courses. The evaluation process is integrated and collaborative: a committee assesses the student project, with the resulting grade accounting for 30% of each student's final mark in all courses for that term. This method fosters essential skills such as teamwork, organisation, and communication, and encourages sustained interaction between students and faculty in a cooperative learning environment.

The interviewee said that there was significant resistance during the implementation of IAW. Initially, the curriculum proposal was rejected by the institution's academic board, which argued that the structure was unsuitable for an engineering degree. The course was eventually approved after persistent dialogue and justification, though opposition persisted, especially from early faculty members. One experienced professor notably declared that "this was not an engineering course" and refused to participate in the first TAI week. Over time, after witnessing the effectiveness of the method and the depth of student learning, he became one of its strongest proponents.

Other faculty members hesitated to assign part of their course grades to a collective project. To address this, the leadership organised technical visits and invited experts to lecture, gradually winning over sceptical professors.

According to the interviewee report, despite growing acceptance, maintaining the IAW strategy requires ongoing effort, which demands continuous collaboration and extra dedication from all involved. The IAW projects are more than simple science fair displays—they are genuine engineering challenges that require scientific justification, material selection, cost analysis, and functional proof. Students must defend their work before a panel, explaining the reasoning behind their design choices. This process develops their confidence, communication skills, and collaboration abilities. The interviewee mentioned that one impactful example involved a simulation project for a Baja car, which attracted the attention of a local entrepreneur and opened the door for potential partnerships.

As reported by the interviewee, students often express frustration over the heavy workload during the semester. Nevertheless, they consistently acknowledge the value of the experience at its conclusion. Faculty also observe that IAW motivates students to seek advanced knowledge early, breaking the monotony of theory-heavy instruction.

Regarding the main benefits of IAW, the interviewee mentioned that the program includes additional short courses on topics such as 3D modelling and optimisation, thereby enriching the students' learning experience. One of the initiative's results is earning course awards at academic conferences and achieving international recognition. The initiative promotes integration among students, faculty, administrative staff, and the wider community. It requires careful planning, teamwork, and adherence to strict deadlines. Administrative staff even evaluate student presentations, reinforcing the collaborative spirit of the program. Due to its success, the IAW model has been adapted to the technical high school curriculum, where project-based evaluation now plays a central role in the curriculum. This success has also inspired other campuses to experiment with active learning methods on a smaller scale, as sweeping reforms often face resistance. Faculty are encouraged to try new approaches without fear of failure, always striving to enhance educational quality.

4.2 Case 2: Competence and Project-based curriculum in Electronic Engineering - Federal University of Itajubá (UNIFEI) - Itajubá campus

The second case study presents the experience of modernising the Electronic Engineering program at UNIFEI (Federal University of Itajubá), Brazil. This program began in 2010 and gained momentum in 2018, thanks to support from the Capes-Fulbright Undergraduate Modernisation Program. The primary objective was to implement Project-Based Learning (PBL) to integrate practical activities throughout students' academic journey, preparing them for professional challenges with hands-on experience in project development.

As the interviewee reported, UNIFEI has a long-standing tradition of emphasising practical education. The Electronic Engineering program, established in 2010, incorporated Problem-Based Learning (PBL) from the outset. The curriculum was designed to immerse students in long-term, complex projects, such as developing electronic boards and devices, as well as simulating real-world engineering challenges. This approach exposed the complete project cycle, from layout to fabrication and testing.

As reported by the interviewee, the program underwent several restructurings over the years, notably in 2015 and 2018, to enhance professional training and integrate practical knowledge with theoretical foundations. The 2018 reforms, supported by Capes-Fulbright, introduced a competency-based curriculum rather than a content-driven one (Almeida et al., 2021) — these changes aligned with new engineering curricular guidelines, emphasising practical skills in telecommunications and instrumentation. Greater flexibility in elective courses was also introduced.

The curriculum reform aimed to align competencies and content with market needs and regulatory guidelines. The structuring teaching nucleus (NDE) adopted three key guidelines or methodologies to support the development of the program's pedagogical project. The first was competency-based education, intended to

create a coherent structure that connects the graduate profile, required skills, and curricular content, drawing on the CDIO methodology and the new DCNs. The second was Bloom's Revised Taxonomy, which defined the expected proficiency levels for graduates in each competency and skill, considering both knowledge acquisition and cognitive development. The third guideline focused on gradually increasing student responsibility. To apply this principle, course structures were designed to promote the transition from passive to active learning, empowering students to take ownership of their educational journey. The PETRA model informed the overall curricular design, incorporating the PBL methodology (Almeida et al., 2021).

According to the interviewee report, technological trends and market demands were key considerations in adapting the curriculum. For instance, the growing importance of Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) was acknowledged, although they were not yet widely used. The course structure shifted to focus on shaping graduates capable of designing technological solutions, rather than merely following traditional engineering approaches. This evolution was not linear; continuous adjustments ensured the curriculum remained relevant to academic and industry standards.

Developing the curriculum involved defining necessary competencies and skills. The initial research phase lasted about eight months, during which faculty collaborated to align content with competency requirements. Drafting the first version of the curriculum took a week, followed by three to four weeks of refinement and revision.

As mentioned by the interviewee, the graduate profile was categorised into three potential roles: developer, designer, and manager, allowing students to prioritise one. Competencies were divided into technical (hardware development, programming) and non-technical (communication, teamwork) categories — the revised Bloom's Taxonomy structured learning objectives ensured efficiency by reducing unnecessary overlaps between courses. The content was integrated, eliminating traditional subject divisions to optimise learning and better prepare students for the job market.

As reported by the interviewee, the 2021 curriculum was structured to reinforce student knowledge through intentional repetition. Encountering the subject multiple times ensured mastery rather than reliance on memorisation. Classroom hours were reduced in favor of increased practical activities and lab sessions, fostering applied learning. This change also provided students with more time for internships and projects, thereby enhancing their flexibility and engagement with real-world experiences. The curriculum emphasised competency development, ensuring each course contributed directly to professional growth. A humanistic education component was also incorporated, integrating courses on communication, economics, and ethics to cultivate socially responsible engineers.

Competency validation was conducted through discussions with alumni and faculty researchers, ensuring alignment with industry trends. A strategic reorganisation of subjects reduced the total curriculum workload from 3,800 to 3,600 hours. Introductory courses were integrated into technical courses to create greater synergy. For example, differential equations and calculus were incorporated into control and electromagnetism courses, optimising class time without compromising essential content.

The program's structure followed a progressive learning path, beginning with general and theoretical courses and advancing toward practical applications and projects. Specific PBL modules facilitated the systematic development of skills. The evolution of the curriculum involved continuous revisions and faculty discussions aimed at maintaining relevance. Some courses remained mandatory due to regulatory requirements or their technical significance. In contrast, others were converted into electives or eliminated if they did not contribute to the desired competencies, resulting in a more flexible and coherent curriculum that supports the development of skills aligned with the profession's needs and expectations for student achievement.

According to the interviewee report, the project-based courses in the Electronic Engineering program offer a structured learning experience that focuses on real-world applications. To ensure that engineering students are exposed to design techniques from day one, four first-year courses were adapted to integrate peer instruction into their teaching methodology. The ELTA00 course introduces circuits and analogue electronics, while ELTA01 builds on this foundation by advancing to diode and transistor circuits. ELTE01 covers scientific methodology and learning theory, fostering metacognitive skills and peer learning, and ELTE02 focuses on human-machine interaction, emphasising usability and empathy in design.

In the third semester, the PBLE00 course introduces the first open-ended project, in which students design a robust physical protection system for an electronic device while ensuring proper heat dissipation.

PBLE01 (fourth semester) and PBLE02 (fifth semester) are interconnected, with PBLE01 focusing on hardware development and PBLE02 focusing on software implementation for the same product. Industry-standard tools are used and updated annually, allowing students to gain relevant hands-on experience. Teams of three start with predefined requirements to ensure project continuity between courses. PBLE02 course is dedicated explicitly to firmware development, with students first creating a self-testing tool for production lines and later implementing a complete human-computer interface.

In the sixth semester, the PBLE03 course involves designing a current-loop-based measurement system using only analog components. Students address precision, stability, and sensor reproducibility while working on circuit design, instrumentation, and analog electronics.

The PBLE04 course introduces FPGA-based development in the seventh semester through a Software-Defined Radio (SDR) project. This course integrates signal modulation, telecommunications theory, and FPGA technologies, thereby strengthening competencies in telecommunications and firmware development.

Finally, in the eighth semester, the PBLE05 course focuses on project management and entrepreneurship. Students explore launching and managing a hardware-based company, understanding the relationship between product development, administration, production, and marketing. Project management methodologies are also covered, preparing students for real-world business challenges.

According to the interviewee report, a crucial aspect of the curriculum was its emphasis on lifelong learning. A dedicated course taught students effective study methods, which are essential for adapting to the new teaching model. The redesigned curriculum strikes a balance between theoretical knowledge and practical experience, aligning with job market demands and preparing students for future challenges.

By shifting from traditional lecture-based teaching to a competency-focused, hands-on approach, UNIFEI's Electronic Engineering program ensures graduates are well-equipped to navigate the evolving engineering landscape. Integrating practical activities, market-driven competencies, and humanistic education cultivates well-rounded professionals who are capable of innovating and leading in their field.

5 Discussion

The two case studies presented — Integrative Academic Work in Mechanical Engineering at the Federal Institute of Minas Gerais (IFMG) and the Competence and Project-Based Curriculum in Electronic Engineering at the Federal University of Itajubá (UNIFEI) — illustrate different approaches to implementing Project-Based Learning (PBL) within engineering education in Brazil. Both cases align with the theoretical framework that emphasises competency-based education, active methodologies, and curricular integration to meet labour market demands and national educational guidelines.

The IFMG-Arcos approach relies on a mandatory subject (IAW) spanning all ten semesters, integrating learning through interdisciplinary projects. This model ensures that PBL remains a consistent and central component of the student's educational experience. In contrast, UNIFEI adopts a more modular approach, embedding PBL principles within specific courses that progressively develop competencies throughout the program. While IFMG focuses on a single integrative framework, UNIFEI structures PBL through competency-based development, aligning each course with a defined skill set.

Both cases encountered faculty resistance during implementation. At IFMG, scepticism was initially strong, with some faculty members questioning whether the approach was suitable for an engineering program. Over time, technical visits, expert lectures, and demonstrated student success contributed to increasing faculty acceptance. At UNIFEI, the faculty played a crucial role in shaping the curriculum, defining competencies, and structuring content around real-world engineering challenges. The success of both models underscores the importance of faculty engagement and continuous professional development in facilitating curriculum reforms.

Both institutions emphasise the importance of real-world application in engineering education. IFMG's IAW model enables students to tackle engineering challenges, such as designing Baja car simulations, which attract the attention of industry professionals. Similarly, UNIFEI ensures market alignment by integrating emerging technological trends, such as FPGA-based development and software-defined radio projects. By reducing classroom hours and increasing hands-on activities, UNIFEI's curriculum better prepares students for the demands of the industry.

Implementing PBL in both institutions required overcoming significant resistance from faculty and institutional boards. The IFMG case highlights the importance of maintaining persistent dialogue and gradually involving faculty, while the UNIFEI case underscores the role of structured discussions and research-driven curriculum development. A common challenge in both cases is the heavy workload associated with PBL. IFMG students initially express frustration but later recognise the value of hands-on learning. Similarly, UNIFEI students experience a gradual shift toward greater autonomy, supported by structured competency development.

Maintaining PBL effectiveness requires continuous effort. At IFMG, ongoing collaboration among faculty, students, and administrative staff ensures that IAW remains a cornerstone of the program. At UNIFEI, iterative curriculum adjustments based on industry feedback help sustain the relevance of the competency-based approach. Both cases demonstrate that successful PBL implementation is not a one-time reform but a continuous process of adaptation and refinement.

6 Conclusion

These case studies reinforce the broader theoretical perspective that active methodologies enhance student engagement, knowledge retention, and employability when well-integrated into the curriculum. The IFMG model demonstrates the potential for interdisciplinary, institution-wide project integration, while UNIFEI's approach showcases how structured competency-based education can drive student development.

The success of these models suggests that future engineering programs should consider ensuring faculty buy-in through professional development and exposure to successful PBL implementations, aligning with industry trends to ensure that graduates possess relevant skills. This should involve integrating assessment strategies that reflect real-world problem-solving and collaboration and providing institutional support to sustain curriculum reforms over time. By addressing these factors, engineering programs can effectively transition toward innovative, competency-based education that aligns with contemporary societal and market needs.

From the perspective of the Innovations in Engineering Teaching Observatory Research Project, the analysis of these two cases brings essential reflections on how curricular innovation occurs in this context. However, it is necessary to note that this research has limitations, and the generalisation of the results presented here is also restricted to the context from which they originated. Given the complexity of curricular innovations, faculty members and administrators from different institutions must consider their specific characteristics and determine which approaches best fit their respective contexts.

Furthermore, it is essential to highlight that this research is still ongoing and will incorporate data collection from faculty members at institutions involved in the project, as a strategy to investigate how these practices influence the classroom, an essential locus of analysis for understanding the phenomenon in question.

References

- Almeida, R. M. A., Veloso, G. F. C., Spadoti, D. H., Ferreira, L. H. C., Müller, E. L., Pereira, R. R., & Vermaas, L. L. G. (2021). Projeto institucional de modernização (PIM) da Engenharia Eletrônica da UNIFEI. In D. R. Leiva, A. C. Seabra, & V. F. de Oliveira (Orgs.), *Planejamento e primeiros resultados dos projetos institucionais de modernização da graduação em engenharia (2019/20)* (pp. 21–48). ABENGE.
- Gonçalves, C. A., & Meirelles, A. de M. (2002). *Projetos e relatórios de pesquisa em administração*. Editora UFMG.
- Helle, L., Tynjälä, P., & Olkinuora, E. (2006). Project-based learning in post-secondary education: Theory, practice and rubber sling shots. *Higher Education*, 51(2), 287–314. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-004-6386-5>
- Keller-Franco, E., & Masetto, M. T. (2018). Currículo por projetos: Repercussões para a inovação na educação superior e no ensino de engenharia. *Revista Espaço do Currículo*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.22478/ufpb.1983-1579.2018v1n11.28548>
- Powell, P., & Weenk, W. (2003). *Project-led engineering education*. Lemma Publishers.
- Vieira Júnior, N. (2018). Project-based curriculum: A course of engineering conceived by integrative academic works. *Revista de Ensino de Engenharia*, 37(2).
- Vieira Júnior, N., Esteves, O. de A., Veraldo Júnior, L. G., Gomes, A. P., Boito, D., Brum, E., Lopes Júnior, L. da S., Fiori, S., Fernandes, V. M. C., Pravia, Z. M. C., Sousa, P. F. B. de, Assis, E. G., & Ferlin, E. P. (2017). Currículo baseado em projetos. In A. M. Tonini (Org.), *Desafios da educação em engenharia: Formação acadêmica e atuação profissional, práticas pedagógicas e laboratórios remotos* (pp. 36–59). ABENGE.
- Weenk, W., & van der Blij, M. (2011). Tutors and teachers in project-led engineering education: A plea for PLEE tutor training. In N. van Hattum-Janssen, R. M. Lima, & D. Carvalho (Orgs.), *Third International Symposium on Project Approaches in Engineering Education (PAEE'2011): Aligning engineering education with engineering challenges*. Department of Production and Systems, PAEE Association, School of Engineering, University of Minho.
- Yin, R. K. (2005). *Estudo de caso: Planejamento e métodos* (3ª ed.). Bookman.